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THE INVESTMENTS AND SECURITIES ACT 2007 ON INSIDER DEALING OFFENCES IN THE NIGERIAN CAPITAL MARKET: AN APPRAISAL

Onuh Paul Igoche, PhD, Nestor Ikeagu, PhD***

ABSTRACT

Capital market and its effective regulation is critical to the development of any economy. Thus inadequacy or absence of strong legal framework is detrimental to its stability and efficiency as it creates an avenue for abuses, malpractices and other unethical conducts by participants in the market. The Nigerian capital market like its counterparts across the globe are regulated by laws, rules and regulations which ensure fair and orderliness in the market and engender investors' confidence to effectively participate in the market. However, advancement in technology and the quest for acquisition of wealth through fraudulent means have made some captains of industries and market operators to engage in all forms of market abuse. This paper therefore examined the adequacy of the provisions of the Investments and Securities Act 2007 (ISA 2007) on insider dealing vis-à-vis the constraints in enforcement of insider dealing offences in the Nigerian capital market. In doing so, the doctrinal research methodology was applied. The paper finds that the provisions of the ISA 2007 on insider dealing are inadequate as section 111 particularly is more of a descriptive provision rather than prescriptive and does not cover all the

spheres/scope of insider dealing offences. Further the ISA 2007 criminalized insider dealing offences without alternatively giving the regulator (SEC) the discretion to use civil sanctions to augment the criminal punishment. It thus recommended the amendment of sections 111 and 113 to widen the scope of the offences of insider dealing in the Nigerian capital market. Furthermore, the paper recommends an amendment of S.115 to impose civil penalties.

Keywords: ISA 2007, Insider Dealing, Capital Market, Offences, Enforcement and Regulation and Prosecution.

1.0 INTRODUCTION

Capital market and its regulation are crucial to the development of any economy, as it affords a wider participation in the economy by investors, who partake in investment opportunities and businesses. The Nigerian capital market like other capital markets around the globe are regulated and guided by laws, rules and regulations, which are abided to by market participants. The laws ensure fair and orderly market and engender investors' confidence to effectively participate in the market, thereby contributing to the development and growth of the economy. The advancement in technology and quest for acquisition of wealth through fraudulent means has made captains of industries and market participants to engage in all forms of market abuses; and it has been the bane of an efficient capital market and its regulation. The challenges of insider dealing and market abuse generally have been a concern to regulators globally and measures are continually being put in place to combat and close the gaps through enactment of laws. Market abuse is an unlawful behaviour in the capital market and it consists of market manipulation, insider dealing and false reporting/ publication of false, misleading and or deceptive statement. The concept of insider dealing is where a person who is an insider in a company has information not available to other investors, makes use of that information for personal gain or to avoid loss, or for the benefit of a third party mostly financial. It is when a person in possession of inside price sensitive information uses it to deal or to encourage or induce another to do so. Investments and Securities Act 2007¹ defines the concept of insider dealing to mean when a person or group who are in possession of confidential and price sensitive information not available to the general public utilizes such information to buy or sell securities for their benefit. Also, the Act² made provisions on insider dealing offences, defences and sanctions in the Nigerian capital market. Any dealing in securities while in possession of price sensitive information not made public is prohibited under the Investments and Securities

*LL.B BL., LL.M. Ph.D. Associate Professor And Head Of Commercial Law, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria. Email: onupaul3@gmail.com. Phone: 08033597303

**LL.B, BL. LL.M PH.D Research Scholar And Assistant. Phone: 08023218640

¹ Act No. 29; section 315

² Sections 111-116 of the ISA.

Act 2007 and the term dealing in securities includes act of buy or sell securities, subscribing, buying, selling or agreeing to subscribe.

Instance of insider dealing abuse is where a director of a company in anticipation of a takeover bid of another small company, arranged the acquisition on his own behalf of shares of the small company through a third party before the takeover bid. Another instance is where a director of a company is aware of the board's decision to close down a veritable part of the company's business, which would shrink its production and profit. An inside information not made known to the public. The director informed his close associate to dispose his shareholding in the company and arranged with a stockbroker to dispose his family shareholding in the company.

Insider dealing, among other market abuses, has always been a topic of controversy surrounded with scandal and destruction of reputations and its consequences have been felt in many jurisdictions around the globe³ Insider dealing and other market abuse have raised serious concern in the Nigerian capital market and the statutory regulator SEC has towed the line of some regulators in other jurisdictions to introduce rules and regulations as a means of bringing the perpetrators who trade on insider information or involved in market abuse to justice. However, the enforcement of insider dealing remains a daunting task and poses challenges to the regulatory authority in the Nigerian capital market in terms of constraints in detection, investigation, prosecution of cases on insider dealing and sanctions.

The aim of this paper is to examine the concept of insider dealing abuses with the specific objective of appraising the legal framework as it relates to the concept. To achieve this, the paper attempts to examine the provisions of the ISA 2007 on insider dealing, particularly the offences and defences; and the challenges in the enforcement of insider dealing offences, the paper concludes by proffering solutions to overcome the challenges.

2.0 CONCEPTUAL DISCOURSE

In discussing the provisions of ISA 2007 on insider dealing and challenges of its enforcement in the Nigerian capital market, certain terms are central to the topic and these

³ Chitimira H. (2004) A Historical Overview of the Regulations of Market Abuse in South Africa, PER/PELJ 2014 (17)3.

deserve special discourse due to their technical meaning and will remain a recurring reference points throughout the paper. It is therefore ideal to briefly discuss their theoretical meaning for better understanding and comprehension of the subject matter. The terms are the Nigerian capital market, Insider and Unpublished price sensitive information.

a. THE NIGERIAN CAPITAL MARKET

Capital market is a market for buying and selling of securities, equity and debt, instruments such as shares and bonds. The instruments are issued to raise medium and long-term financing from investing public by government and corporate entities to facilitate new projects. According to Goldman Sachs, 'Capital markets match the demand for funds with the supply of funds. These markets fuel economic growth by allocating capital that can be used to create jobs, build infrastructure and financing innovative ideas'⁴. Capital market has two segments, that is, the primary market where new securities (stocks and bonds) issued are sold to investors by corporate entities and government wishing to raise funds from the capital market, and the secondary market where the existing securities bought by investors at the initial public offer sell or trade them. Secondary market is a market for trading of existing securities and the trading platform is called the exchange. The equity (stock) and bond market form the major portion of capital market; however other financial instruments traded in the capital market include futures, derivatives, contracts, options *etcetera*.

The Nigerian capital market in its entirety is regulated by SEC. In addition, the Nigerian Stock Exchange now NGX Limited, FMDQ OTC Securities Exchanges and NASD Plc. OTC Securities Exchanges are self-regulatory organizations in the market that provide trading platforms for their members and ensuring that market abuses are prevented. The NGX Limited provides trading platform for stocks (equities), while FMDQ provides platform for trading on bonds, treasury bills, commercial papers, foreign exchange and derivatives. FMDQ also provides OTC securities exchanges for fixed income, foreign exchange and derivatives market⁵. NASD Plc, provides over the counter securities exchange platform for

⁴ <http://www.goldmansachs.com/s/interactive-guide-to-capital-markets>. Accessed on 31 October 2019.

⁵ See <http://www.fmdq.com/about/history>. Accessed on 19 April 2019.

trading of wide range of instruments including equities, bond and securities not listed on any other exchange in Nigeria such as the NGX Limited⁶. Market abuse can occur in any of these trading platforms and the providers have responsibilities to prevent such occurrence and protect investors from the incidence of market abuse.

b. INSIDER

The concept of Insider is defined by ISA 2007⁷ to mean and include any person who is or is connected with the company during the preceding six (6) months in one of the following capacities: director, an officer, an employee of the company or a related company, an employee of the company involved in a professional or business relationship to the company, any shareholder of the company who own five percent or more of any class of securities or any person who is or can be deemed to have any relationship with the company or member, and members of audit committee of a company.

Insider also includes any individual who by virtue of having been connected with the company as aforementioned has obtained unpublished price sensitive information in relation to the securities of the company⁸. In South Africa, the Financial Market Act, 2012⁹ defines insider to mean a person who has inside information being a director, employee or shareholder of an issuer of securities listed on a regulated market to which the inside information relates or having access to such information by virtue of employment, office or profession, or where such person knows that the direct or indirect source of the information was from a person contemplated above.

By these definitions, the potential pool of persons who could become insiders is relatively large. Apart from director, officers, employees, other persons contracted to render services to the company such as auditors, fiduciaries, advertising agents can be taken as insiders. Also, employees of law firm, banking, auditors, brokerage and printing firm, who were given such information to provide services to the company whose securities they traded could be potential insiders. In addition, family members and relatives of directors, officers and employees who traded the securities after receiving such information are also

⁶ See <http://nasdng.com/contract/fags>. Accessed on 19 April 2019.

⁷ Section 315

⁸ Brazier G. (1996) *Insider Dealing: Law and Regulation*, Cavendish Publishing Limited, Great Britain, p 111

⁹ Section 77

potential insiders as well as persons who traded for gain on information obtained by over-hearing company's director in a lift or in a social gathering discussing unpublished price sensitive information.

Also, government employees who learned of such information because of their employment by the government can as well be an insider. Therefore, the definition of insider in one jurisdiction can be wider than the other in another jurisdiction based on the provisions of the applicable laws, and may cover not only insiders themselves but also any person related to them such as broker, associates, family members' *etcetera*. The reason for the wide scope of envisaged insiders is the seriousness of its negative impact in the capital market and for the people with fiduciary and quasi fiduciary obligations not to have excuses or lee way. In addition, it is important to regulate insider dealing as it impinges on the transparency, integrity and investors' confidence of the market. If insiders are not regulated to make use of their inside knowledge, there would not be a level playing field for all investors to operate in the market. Insider dealing is unjust enrichment and dishonest behaviour of people with fiduciary or quasi fiduciary obligations taking advantages of their favoured position. The mischief which insider dealing aims at preventing is that those close to the company should not be allowed to abuse their position by making use of information in their possession, which concerns securities of that company, to some personal advantage¹⁰

c. UNPUBLISHED, PRICE SENSITIVE INFORMATION

Insider dealing offence is generally based on misuse of information which relates to securities of a public company. The term unpublished price sensitive information is not clearly defined in the ISA 2017, but was mentioned in passing under Insider definition¹¹ as thus;

"...and any reference to unpublished price sensitive information in relation to any securities of a company is a reference to information which:

¹⁰ Brazier, G. (1996) *Insider Dealing: Law and Regulation*, Cavendish Publishing Limited, Great Britain, pp76-77.

¹¹ Section 315

(i) relates to specific matters relating or of concern (directly or indirectly) to that company, that is, is not of a general nature relating or of concern to that company; and

(ii) is not generally known to those persons who are accustomed to or would be likely to deal in those securities but which would, if it were generally known to them be likely materially to affect the price of those securities.

From the above, it could be deduced as information that has not been released to the public and not in public knowledge or domain, which is only known by insiders, it is inside information that has not been made public. The Financial Market Act 2012 of South Africa¹², defines inside information to mean specific or precise information, which has not been made public and which is obtained or learned as an insider; and if it were made public would be likely to have a material effect on the price or value of any securities listed on a regulated market.

In the United Kingdom, under the Criminal Justice Act 1993¹³ inside information is defined to mean information which relates to particular securities or to a particular issuer(s) of securities and not to securities or to issuers of securities generally. It is information that is specific or precise; has not been made public; and if it were made public would likely to have a significant effect on the price of any securities. It is dealing in securities on the basis of insider information that is not yet publicly known and which would affect the price of the securities if it were made public.

It could therefore be said that inside information has essential elements or characteristics which includes, that the information must be specific or precise and not a mere rumour, precise information that should be narrow, exact and definitive, in order not to run the risk of unduly and unreasonably inhibiting the analytical relationship and assessment of companies that are much in the interest of investors in the market. Other essential elements are that the information has not been made public and that the information must be such that would be likely to have significant effect on the price of any securities if it is made public. In addition, the term unpublished price sensitive information is akin to

¹² Section 77 n. 3

¹³ 1993 c6; section 56.

“material and non-public information” which is the term used under Securities law of the United States¹⁴.

Under the Securities Act of United States, information is material if a reasonable investor is likely to consider it’s significant in making an investment decision or if the information is reasonably certain to have a substantial impact on the market price of company’s securities. Therefore, price sensitive information is material information that can effect or impact on the share price of the company and may include financial data, changes in the executives of the company through appointments or resignation, even incapacity of strategic senior director due to serious long term illness, acquisition or loss of contract, products malfunction, defaults, liquidation *etcetera*. Certainly, price sensitive information not made public but privately obtained from insider is unpublished and if one goes ahead to make an investment decision which one would otherwise not have made at that time one would have contravened section 111 of the ISA¹⁵.

3.0 INSIDER DEALING

According to ISA 2007¹⁶ ‘insider dealing includes insider trading and occurs when a person or group of persons who being in possession of some confidential and price sensitive information not generally available to the public utilizes such information to buy or sell securities for the benefit of himself, itself or any person’. Insider dealing is the use of privileged information for purpose of gain or to avoid loss at the expense of the unsuspecting investors. The term insider dealing is often used interchangeably with insider trading; it is the same with insider trading as they have the same elements and features. In United Kingdom insider dealing is used as in Nigeria¹⁷, while the term insider trading is adopted in United States and South Africa¹⁸.

Insider dealing happens when a trade, either sale or buy, has been influenced by the privileged possession of corporate information that has not yet been made public. When a

¹⁴ The Securities Act of 1933

¹⁵ No 29 of 2007

¹⁶ Section 315

¹⁷ Financial Services Act 2012, Criminal Justice Act 1993. See also The Company Securities (Insider Dealing) Act 1985 (1985 c8).

¹⁸ Securities Act 1933 and Securities Exchange Act of 1934; and Financial Markets Act 19 of 2012, South Africa.

person uses price sensitive information, he has knowledge of, which is unpublished or not known to public to trade on public company shares and gain unfair advantage over the rest of the market. It includes a practice in which an insider or related party trades based on unpublished price sensitive information obtained during the performance of insider's duties or responsibilities in the company, or in breach of a fiduciary or other relationship of trust and confidence or where the non-public information was misused or misappropriated from the company. Trading of public company's shares or other securities i.e. bonds or options by individuals with access to unpublished or non-public information about the company is prohibited. However, trading by company's insiders such as directors, principal officers, key employees and large shareholders may be legal, if the trading is done in a way that does not take advantage of unpublished information and such trades are disclosed or reported to the regulators in accordance with the extant laws.

In a transparent market, information is disseminated in a manner by which all market participants receive it at the same time. Therefore, using unpublished information or non-public information for making trade or avoiding a loss disturbs fairness, orderliness and transparency, which are the basis of a capital market. Insider dealing always involves scandals and reputational risk and jurisdictions strive hard to eradicate this practice and contend with its threat to fair, orderly and integrity of the market as it affords a relatively small privilege minority, an unfair advantage over the vast majority of investors who do not enjoy the same equality of information or opportunity.

Regulators around the globe, like US SEC, have put in measures to check the incidence of insider dealing. The United States Securities and Exchange Commission introduced rules¹⁹ forcing all United States companies to provide access to their insider transaction filing on their corporate websites commencing in June 2003.

Also, it reduced the dealing period for two days following the day which the transaction is executed and pushed for the enactment of Insider Trading and Securities Fraud Enforcement Act of 1988²⁰. More so, in Nigeria, SEC approved the Nigerian Stock Exchange

¹⁹ Release no: 34-47809, 35-27674 IC-26044, File No: S7-52-02, June 30, 2003.

²⁰ This Act amended the US Securities Act 1934 on civil sanctions for insider trading and allows US SEC to impose stiff monetary penalties up to \$1 million.

Rules²¹ which placed a restriction on directors, persons discharging managerial responsibility or advisers of the issuer and their connected persons from trading in the issuer's securities, where they possess unpublished price sensitive information. The NGX Rule has led to introduction of a 'closed period', which is a period during which the aforementioned principal officers and connected persons are prevented or denied the ability to trade in the issuer's securities in certain events, that is, declaration of financial results (quarterly, half-yearly and annual), declaration of dividend (both interim and final), major expansion plan, any form of amalgamation, issue of securities by way of public offer or right, bonus *etcetera*.

Some notable decided cases of insider dealing are thus: *R v. Cross*²², the court was called upon to determine when a share dealing is criminal. Mr. Cross had been the managing director of Wordplex Plc but sold shares in that company shortly before a new issue of shares, which had the effect of bringing down their price, he was convicted of insider dealing and fined £7,000 on appeal however, the conviction was quashed by Court of Appeal on the grounds that the Crown Court judge had misdirected the jury, confirming that it is open to the jury to find that the accused had proved that he had not used the price sensitive information to make any profit or avoid any loss. Again, courts were called upon to determine whether professionals, independent contractors and their employees contracted to offer services could be held liable for insider dealing offence, in *R v Geoffrey Collier*²³, the defendant an adviser who was then head of securities of City of London finance house, Morgan Grenfell which had been retained by a client to advise on a takeover bid. When the bid was about to be completed in 1986, the defendant arranged the acquisition in London on his own behalf of shares of the target company, which he perfected through a company registered in the Cayman Island prior to the announcement of the bid and was subsequently convicted on pleading guilty of insider dealing. He was fined £25,000 and was ordered to pay £7,000 in cost with a prison sentence of 12 months being suspended for two years.

²¹ The NSE Rule approved by SEC on 19 May, 2014. Now The Nigerian Exchange Rules

²² (1991) BCLC 125CA; (1990) BCC 237; (1990) 91 Cr App R 115 (CA).

²³ (1987) Unreported, see The New York Times (National Edition), 2 July 1987 Section D, p.7; or The Times (London) July 2, 1987 at p.1, col.8.

Again, in the case of *Christopher McQuoid*²⁴, a Solicitor employed as General Counsel at TTP Communications in May 2006, was told confidentially that Motorola was planning a takeover bid for TTP. He passed that information to his father in-law James Melbourne. Two days before the deal was publicly announced, Melbourne bought shares at 13 pence each, the takeover price was 45 pence a share and Melbourne profit was close to £50,000. Three months later, he gave a cheque for exactly half the gain to McQuoid. Melbourne trade was spotted as being suspicious and reported to the FSA. He was prosecuted and was sentenced to eight months. Melbourne, aged 75, was given same sentence, but suspended for 12 months.

Also, in *Dirks v SEC*²⁵, the court held that insiders include independent contractors who owe a fiduciary duty, apart from directors, officers, employees are termed constructive insiders. Again, in *SEC vs. Materia*,²⁶ a financial printing firm proof reader, and clearly not an insider by any definition, was found to have determined the identity of takeover targets based on proofreading tender offer documents during his employment. The Court found him liable for the theft of the information from the employer and use of the information to purchase or sell securities in another entity constituted a fraud in connection with the purchase and sale of securities.

In *SEC v. Joseph Frank Vacante*,²⁷ SEC charged a former employee of a Biotech company with insider trading on confidential information regarding the company's withdrawal of certain products from consideration by the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA). It was alleged by US SEC that Vacante learned that the FDA had recommended that Trinity withdraw two products, which Vacante believed represented the future of the company. It was further alleged that, that same day Vacante twice communicated with his broker in effort to sell Trinity American Depository Receipts (ADRs) which he had received as part of his employment, including lowering the price to ensure the sale occurred. On October 14, 2016 Trinity announced that it was withdrawing the two products from FDA consideration.

²⁴ (2009) 4 All ER 388; see also, *SEC v Ernesto Tapanes*, Litigation Release No. 20431A January 18, 2008 (08-60064) - CIV- DIMITROULEAS (S.D FL.)

²⁵ 463 U.S. 646 (1983); see also *Basic v Levinson*, 485 U.S. 224, 231-32 (1988).

²⁶ 745 F.2d 197 (2d Cir. 1984). Leagle.com. Retrieved 4 June 2019.

²⁷ Litigation Release no. 24406; No. 19-CIV- 1616 CSD N.Y. filed February 21 2019

At the close of trading that day, Trinity's ADRs closed more than 50% lower than the prior day's closing day price. SEC alleges that by selling his ADRs before Trinity's announcement; Vacante avoided a loss of over \$70,000. SEC filed in charges against Vacante in Federal Court in Manhattan. Vacante has consented for settlement to payment of \$70,827 plus interest of \$6,247 and a penalty of \$70,827. On a defence of no expectation of profit or benefit on a charge of insider dealing; in *SEC v Yurt*²⁸, it was held that maintenance of good relationship between co-workers is sufficient to satisfy 'benefit' requirement, while in *SEC v Maxwell*²⁹ the court held that the Executive who tipped his barber was not liable for insider dealing, as he did not stand to benefit from the tip due to their 'relative stations in life'.

3.1 INSIDER DEALING OFFENCES AND DEFENCES

Section 111(1) of the ISA 2007 provides for insider dealing, which prohibits a person who is an insider of a company from buying or selling or otherwise deal in securities of the company, which are offered to the public for sale or subscription if the person has information which he knows is unpublished price sensitive information in relation to those securities. Apart from the insider provided under section 111(1), sub sections 111(2), (4), (5) and (6) prohibit other persons from dealing in company securities in the following situations and circumstances herein mentioned. Where the information is unpublished, that is, where a person has information which he knowingly obtains directly or indirectly from another person who is connected with a particular company, or was at any time within the six months preceding the obtaining of the information so connected³⁰.

Also, where a person is contemplating making a takeover offer for a company in a particular capacity,³¹ or where a person has knowingly obtained directly or indirectly information from an individual who is contemplating or has made a takeover offer of a company in section 111(4)³². In addition, where a person is prohibited by the provisions of section 111 from dealing on an approved securities exchange or capital trade point in any

²⁸ 327 F.3d 1263 (11th Cir. 2013).

²⁹ 341 F. Supp. 2d 941 (S.D OH 2014).

³⁰ Section 111 (2) (a) of the ISA 2007.

³¹ Section 111(4) of ISA 2007

³² Section 111(5) of ISA 2007

securities, the person is barred from counselling or procuring any other person to deal in those securities knowing or having reasonable cause or believe that, that other person would deal in those securities³³.

Moreover, section 112 of the ISA 2007 provides to the effect that section 111 also applies to information held by a public officer or former public officer, and to a person who knowingly obtained any such information directly or indirectly, from a public officer or former public officer who that person knows or has reasonable cause to believe held the information by virtue of his position as public officer. The persons mentioned in section 112 are prohibited from dealing in any relevant securities, counsel or procure any other person to deal in any such securities or communicate to any other person the information held in the aforementioned circumstance, if he knows or has reasonable cause to believe that the person would make use of the information for purpose of dealing in the securities³⁴.

Generally, the basic requirements for establishment of offence of insider dealing, the individual in question must have information as an insider, and he knows that it is an inside information, and he has the information and knows that he has it from an inside source. In addition, the individual must also deal in securities that are price-effected securities in relation to the information; and thirdly the dealing must take place in the dealing circumstances, i.e. on securities exchange, during initial public offer or offer for sale, and on reliance on a professional intermediary³⁵.

However, based on the provisions of sections 111 and 112 of the ISA 2007 it can be deduced that insider dealing offence may occur in the following circumstances:

- 1 An insider trading for his own accounts; an insider who knows that he has insider information and who deals directly or indirectly or through an agent to his own account in the securities listed on a regulated market, which the inside information relates and which are likely to be affected by it.
- 2 An insider who deals for another person, an insider who knows that he has inside information and who deals, directly or indirectly, or through an agent for any other

³³ Section 111(6) of ISA 2007

³⁴ Section 112(3) of ISA 2007

³⁵ Brazier G. (1996) *n. 3*, 131-137.

person in securities listed on a regulated market to which the information relates and which are likely to be affected by it.

- 3 A person who knowingly deals for an insider; a person who deals for an insider directly or indirectly or through an agent in the securities listed on a regulated market to which the inside information possessed by the insider relates or which are likely to be affected by it, and knows that such person is an insider.
- 4 An insider who discloses inside information; an insider who knows that he has inside information and who discloses the inside information to another person.
- 5 An insider who encourages or discourages another person to trade; an insider who knows that he has inside information and who encourages or causes another person to deal or discourages or stops another person from dealing in the securities listed on a regulated market to which the inside information relates or which are likely to be affected by it.

However, in dealing with the defences to the offences of insider dealing, the ISA 2007 in section 113 made provisions for exceptions or defences where the offences would not apply thus:

- (a) A person having information is not prohibited from doing any particular thing if he does not have the intention of making profit or loss, whether for himself or another person by the use of that information³⁶.
- (b) A person having information is not prohibited from entering into a transaction in the course of the exercise in good faith of his functions as a liquidator, receiver or trustee in bankruptcy.
- (c) Also, a person having information is not prohibited from doing any particular thing if the information was obtained by him in the course of a business of stockbroker in which he was engaged or employed or was of a description which it would be reasonable to expect him to obtain in the ordinary course of that business and he does that in good faith in the course of that business.

³⁶ *SEC vs. Maxwell* n. 10.

(d) In addition, any particular thing in relation to any particular securities, if the information was of a description which it would be reasonable to expect him to obtain in the ordinary course of that business and he does that thing in good faith in the course of that business.

Indeed, as jurisdictions have strived to widen the scope of insider dealing offences in order to bring many people to justice and create a level playing field for all investors, they have also made concerted efforts to tighten up the law and close the loopholes in the defence of the offence of insider dealing. The UK and South Africa have provided statutory defences for the offence of insider dealing, unlike the ISA 2007 which in section 113 as aforementioned, partially made provisions for exceptions. The said exceptions or defences to the offence of insider dealing in section 113 do not generally cover the offences as obtainable in other jurisdictions. In other words, they do not contain relatively generalized provisions which may be applicable where the individual in question dealt in securities or has encouraged another person to deal in securities or has simply disclosed information to a third party otherwise than in an ordinary course of performance of the function of his employment, office or profession.

In the United Kingdom, the Criminal Justice Act³⁷, for instance, provides for defences to the offence of dealing in securities and encouraging another to deal in securities, i.e. no expectation of profit; defences to the offence of disclosure of information to another, no expectation of dealing; and special defence to offence of insider dealing such as market makers, market information and price stabilization.

Also, Financial Market Act of 2012³⁸ in South Africa provides for defence to offences of insider trading to include; earlier instruction that preceded the knowledge and possession of the insider information; all parties had possession of the same inside information at the time of transaction; no benefit from the movement in the price of the securities; trading was limited to the parties to the transaction; authorized user acting on specific instruction of a client without knowing he was insider; and insider information was disclosed because it was expedient to do so for the purpose of the proper performance of the function or his

³⁷ Section 53 of the Criminal Justice Act 1993 (1993 c36).

³⁸ Section 78.

employment, office or profession in circumstances unrelated to dealing in any securities listed.

By and large, the defence to offence of insider dealing in developed and emerging markets around the globe could be summarised thus: the dealing was not expected to result in a profit by virtue of the price sensitive information; it was reasonably believed that the information had been disclosed widely enough to avoid prejudicing other parties to the share transaction; and the person who bought or sold the shares would have done so without the information, because he needed to sell to raise the cash or to come within a permitted dealing period.

3.2 THE CHALLENGES IN ENFORCEMENT OF INSIDER DEALING OFFENCE IN THE NIGERIAN CAPITAL MARKET.

The challenges in enforcement of insider dealing offence start from surveillance and monitoring of trade for detection of unusual price movement; investigation of perceived case of insider dealing; prosecution of the offence in court and penalties/sanctions as statutorily provided.

3.3 DETECTION OF INSIDER DEALING OFFENCE

In the Nigerian capital market, the role of surveillance and monitoring of trade is the responsibilities of exchanges and capital trade points which are usually self-regulatory organizations, such as, the NGX Limited, FMDQ, and NASD. However, SEC has the primary and overall responsibilities of market surveillance and monitoring as the apex regulatory body in the capital market³⁹. Ordinarily, the exchanges and capital trade points are expected to deploy system specifically designed to detect unusual trading volumes and price movements, which could be indicative of insider dealing or market manipulation. For instance, the Department of Market Surveillance and Investigation of the NGX Limited closely monitors all market activities on the exchange. It utilizes a robust surveillance system in detecting and investigating a potential market abuse, infractions on the NGX rules and securities laws especially in areas of insider dealing and market manipulation generally.

³⁹ Idigbe, A.I. (2015) Legal Issues in Capital Market Operation in Nigeria. Distinct Universal Limited, Lagos, 2nd Edition, p81.

The NGX Limited has market surveillance platform powered by NASDAQ's smart surveillance technology, it has the capacity to distil complex information into a single snapshot that provides clear guidance on where to focus an investigation. Also, it correlates real time and historical data with detection patterns to ensure easy detection of unusual trading pattern that could be potential insider dealing abuse or breaches of exchange trading rules and practice. In addition, the Smart technology monitors market manipulation, detect and deter manipulative tendencies, gather intelligence, carryout traders' monitoring and analysis, conduct multi-asset and cross market surveillance, and execute risk-based supervision of flagged participants⁴⁰.

The exchanges keep surveillance over securities trading, by the means they are able to identify and investigate suspicious dealing most especially on securities and dealings prior to takeover and mergers. Where unusual activity is detected and there appear to be no obvious cause, the relevant exchange may conduct enquiry from the directors of listed companies on any price sensitive information, and if there is likely case of insider dealing the exchange is required to further investigate and report same to SEC. In fact, apart from reporting detection of unusual trading to SEC, the exchanges and capital trade points are also mandated to render trade activities report daily, weekly, quarterly, and yearly to SEC, in addition to engaging professionals and building capacity in manning the systems and ensuring the effective surveillance roles. SEC on its part, is expected to continually analyse the reports and make inquiries on unusual trading patterns. SEC as well has the facility for monitoring trades on line real time in some exchanges from its head office.

Indeed, one of the challenges of detection of insider dealing in the Nigerian capital market is ability to sustain constant maintenance of surveillance equipment/gadgets to avoid system breakdown and uninterrupted services of surveillance; and ability to engage professionals and build capacity in manning the systems and ensuring the effective/efficient surveillance roles by regulators and self-regulatory organizations. There are sometimes the Nigeria market experience systems interruption on monitoring of trades due to system breakdown occasioned by lack of maintenance in the surveillance

⁴⁰ [http://: www.nse.com.ng](http://www.nse.com.ng). Accessed on 16 April, 2019.

equipment/gadgets and dearth in engagement of highly technical experts on conduct of market surveillance and operation of system in monitoring insider dealing and market abuse generally.

3.4 INVESTIGATION OF INSIDER DEALING OFFENCE.

Based on the Complaint Management Framework recently introduced in the Nigerian capital market by SEC⁴¹, where surveillance of trading activities by the exchange or capital trade point indicate that an usual transaction in securities may have involved insider dealing; the matter would be preliminarily investigated and if there is likelihood or substantial evidence for offence of insider dealing, it would be referred to SEC⁴², which may conduct further inquiry and full investigation before referring same to criminal prosecuting authorities as prescribed by ISA 2007.⁴³ However, apart from the aforementioned process SEC can on its initiative, based on trade activities reports or online real time monitoring of trade, commence inquiry or conduct investigation on detection of unusual price movement.

In term of ISA provisions, SEC in carrying its investigation of insider dealing or market abuse generally has restricted powers of interrogation, subpoena, search and seizure of records and documentation as it can call for information from a regulated person or corporate body. However, apart from regulated person/ body corporate SEC can call for information from any person/body corporate and such person/body corporate is under obligation to provide the information; but where such person/body corporate fails to oblige or provide the information SEC does not have the power to sanction such person/ body corporate;⁴⁴ unlike where the law enforcement authorities are involved. After such investigation and fact finding, based on section 304 of the ISA, SEC would refer the matter to criminal prosecuting authority. In addition, it can take administrative actions by voiding the transaction where necessary⁴⁵ and order payment of compensation or any other amount it may determine against a person /body corporate found liable for insider dealing

⁴¹ SEC Rules relating to the Complaint Management Framework of the Nigerian Capital Market, February 2015.

⁴² Rule No. 2 *ibid.*

⁴³ Section 304.

⁴⁴ Section 13(t) of the ISA 2007.

⁴⁵ Section 114

to any aggrieved person who suffered loss based on the act of the person/ body corporate⁴⁶.

Section 304 of ISA 2007, deprived SEC the power of prosecution of criminal offences created under the Act⁴⁷, including insider dealing offences. The practical hurdle of referral and handing over of matters with criminal elements to criminal prosecuting authorities limits SEC's enforcement powers and prompt action of bringing offenders of insider dealing to justice. SEC refers all market abuse cases to either Economic and Financial Crimes Commission (EFCC) or the Nigeria Police, and immediately such referral is made, SEC has no control over the conduct of investigation on the matter. The law enforcement agencies may continue or discontinue with the investigation without any notice to SEC, and the latter can only write to enquire or request for update on the matter. The obvious is that the officers of law enforcement agencies apart from over burden by traditional criminal cases, lack in-depth technical knowledge and expertise on the workings of capital market and securities issues. They usually find it uninteresting and difficult to appreciate the facts of the cases; and most times they abandon or discontinue with investigation or prosecution of a good case on market abuse in the capital market without any cogent reasons, perhaps for lack of understanding and technicalities.

In *SEC v Bonkolans Investments Limited*,⁴⁸ the APC in 2002 found that Mr. Lawrence Okwefuleze, the managing director of Bonkolans Investments Limited took advantage of the dematerialization of shares through setting up of the CSCS Limited then to illegally transfer and sell shares of many companies particularly Nestle Plc and Unilever Plc shares on alleged six hundred million Naira scam on the Nigerian Stock Exchange (now NGX). APC referred the matter to the Nigeria Police, till date no report of investigation or prosecution on the matter, Also, in *FRN v Arinze Nwobu*⁴⁹ the EFCC based on SEC's referral, preferred criminal charges of stealing and breach of trust among others, at the Lagos High Court, against the defendant, former managing director MBA Securities limited, in respect of misappropriation of N33 million paid by Aswani Textile Industries Plc to its bond holders,

⁴⁶ Section 116

⁴⁷ ISA 2007

⁴⁸ APC/21/2002

⁴⁹ ID/53c/2012 (Unreported)

through MBA Securities limited as Trustee to the Debenture, in repayment of Aswani Textile Industries Plc Redeemable Debenture Stock 1995/98. The matter was struck out on technicalities and EFCC has not made effort to relist the matter⁵⁰.

Again, the more worrisome trend in investigation of insider dealing and other market abuses cases is political interference with the process of investigation and prosecution. Where captains of industry, highly placed political individuals and their associates are under investigation for alleged offence of market abuse, or in particular insider dealing offence, there is always pressure from the political class to suppress the investigation and close the matter to avoid damage of reputation or embarrassment of the highly placed individuals and government.

In *SEC v AP Plc. & Ors.*,⁵¹ on alleged concealment of N26 billion and omission of material information on the prospectus. The managing director and other directors of the company failed to attend the APC proceedings, even when it was escalated to the Presidency. Also, they failed to attend the proceedings of Tribunal of Inquiry headed by Justice Edet Robert Nkop (Rtd.)⁵², and till date the directors have not been brought to book.

Again, in *SEC v Cadbury Nigeria Plc & 20 Ors.*⁵³ in respect of financial misstatements in the published accounts of Cadbury (Nig.) Plc (2002-2005) to the tune of over N4 billion. APC conceded to the application of leading counsel to 1st, 2nd, 5th-19th respondents to amend its memorandum of facts and remove all sections of the ISA 1999 violated that had criminal elements to enable his clients submit to the jurisdiction of APC. The APC punished the respondents based on the breaches of the then SEC Rules and Regulations 2007, that is, Rule 3(4), Rule 7, Rule 11, Rule 204 *etcetera*, which are more of civil contraventions.

⁵⁰ See also *SEC v Afroil PLC & 13 Ors.* (APC/1/2008), where APC referred Mr. Sanni Olakunle, the managing director of Afroil Plc and the company to EFCC for alleged illegal sale of the company's shares and misleading press statements. Till date no report of criminal investigation or prosecution against the company or its managing director.

⁵¹ APC/22/2002

⁵² The Tribunal was inaugurated on 8th August, 2002 to investigate allegations of mismanagement levelled against the past management of AP Plc, led by Alhaji Umar Abba Gana. The Tribunal submitted its report on February 2003.

⁵³ APC/1/2007

3.5 PROSECUTION AND SANCTIONS/PENALTIES FOR INSIDER DEALING OFFENCES.

The prosecution of Insider dealing offence is the prerogative of law enforcement agencies and office of the Attorney General of the Federation to commence. A decision has to be taken as to whether or not those involved should be prosecuted once a case of alleged insider dealing has been established. SEC does not have any input on the decision or issue of prosecution as it does not possess the mandate; the best it does is to make representation to the office of the Attorney General of the Federation to see reasons in prosecution of an alleged case of insider dealing, unlike in the United Kingdom where Financial Conduct Authority has the power to prosecute a perceived insider dealing offender. Indeed, SEC can initiate administrative proceedings for fact finding and establishment of the violation of sections 111 and 112 of the ISA 2007; which it can void transaction if it deems it necessary and order payment of compensation to an aggrieved person.

However, SEC by the provisions of the ISA 2007 does not have power to impose civil sanction/penalty against a person or body corporate found liable for insider dealing⁵⁴, unlike other jurisdictions, for instance South Africa, where Enforcement Committee of Financial Sector Conduct Authority (FSCA)⁵⁵, can impose administrative penalties on offender and the latter has a right of appeal; or the Directorate of Market Abuse in the name of FSCA can institute a civil claim against a person who traded in a listed security while in possession of inside information, apart from criminal offence charges⁵⁶.

Also, Financial Conduct Authority (FCA) can concurrently use its other enforcement powers and prosecuting power where criminal prosecution may not be sufficient or adequate to address all regulatory implications of the situation. FCA may opt to obtain injunction to prevent further breaches, remedy breaches or secure assets; discipline the firm, approved persons, withdraw the approval or obtain compensation for customers. Moreover, FCA under Financial Service Act 2012 as amended has concurrent prosecution powers with some other prosecuting bodies such as Secretary of State for Trade and

⁵⁴ Sections 115 and 304 of the ISA 2007

⁵⁵ Financial Sector Conduct Authority, effective 1 April 2018.

⁵⁶ Section 99 of Financial Market Act, No. 19 of 2012.

Industry, the Serious Fraud Office, the Crown Prosecution and the Director General Trading for Consumer Credit matters. FCA is empowered to prosecute insider dealing, breaches of money laundering regulations, false or misleading information, destroying or falsifying documents, misleading statements and practices, offences relating to listed securities *etcetera*, against firms, its officers and employees⁵⁷.

Indeed, where a court finds a person/ body corporate liable under section 111 for insider dealing, the punishment under section 115 of the ISA 2007 shall be invoked. The purport of the said provision of section 115, is that any person who contravenes any provisions of Part XI of the ISA 2007 commits an offence and is liable on conviction in the case of a person to a fine of not less than N500, 000.00 or an amount equivalent to double the amount of profit derived by him or loss averted by the use of the information obtained in contravention or to imprisonment for a term not exceeding seven years.

However, in the case of body corporate, a fine not less than N1,000,000.00 or an amount equivalent to twice the amount of profit derived by it or loss averted by the use of the information obtained in contravention. It is submitted that the monetary penalties herein are not adequate in today's economic realities compare to the seriousness of the offence and are not sufficient to deter persons from getting involved in insider dealing activities.

Moreover, by the pursuant of section 116, SEC or Investments and Securities Tribunal (IST) may order a person liable under Part XI of the ISA, which include insider dealing, to pay compensation to any aggrieved person who suffered a loss by the reason of the actions of the offender. The amount of compensation, which is civil remedy, to be paid or entitled by the aggrieved person shall be the amount of the loss sustained or any other amount as may be determined by SEC or IST. Indeed, this provision on compensation can only be activated after the person has been found liable by SEC or convicted by criminal court of justice. In other words, the aggrieved person can only approach SEC or IST after the offender has been found liable or convicted.

⁵⁷ Freshfields Bruckhaus Deringer on Financial Services: Investigations and Enforcement (2001). Butterworths Lexis Nexis, Reed Elsevier Limited, United Kingdom pp465-478.

4.0 CONCLUSION

Capital market and its effective regulation is critical to the development of any economy, and inadequacy or absence of strong legal framework is detrimental to its stability and efficiency as it creates an avenue for abuses, malpractices and other unethical conducts by participants in the market. As the Nigerian capital market adopts the choice of a combination of public and private sectors participatory regulation (statutory and non-statutory), both sectors have crucial roles to play in combating and curtailing market abuse and instilling effective governance in the Nigerian capital market, to ensure that it is fair, transparent and orderly in order to engender investors' confidence and their continued participation in the market. The paper ventured to examine the provisions of the ISA 2007⁵⁸ on insider dealing and challenges of its enforcement in the Nigerian capital market. It further discussed insider dealing, offences and defences based on provisions of the ISA 2007, with the enforcement challenges such as surveillance and detection, investigation, prosecution and penalties of insider dealing.

Indeed, from all these discussions, it is found that the provisions of the ISA 2007 on insider dealing are inadequate as section 111 particularly is more of a descriptive provision rather than prescriptive and does not cover all the spheres/scopes of insider dealing offences, such as dealing offences and disclosures offences (where an insider discloses information to another otherwise than in the ordinary course or proper performance of his functions of his employment, office or profession), which will give the regulator and prosecutors the avalanche of provisions to rely on in bringing offenders to justice. Also, the exceptions or defences in section 113 are not elaborate to afford the potential offender wide opportunity to defend oneself, such as defence of close circle where all parties had the information at the time of transaction or the trading was limited to the parties to the transaction; and defence of no benefit from the movement in the price of securities *etcetera*.

In addition, based on section 304,⁵⁹ SEC mandatorily refers matters with criminal element(s) to law enforcement agencies, and criminal prosecuting authorities whose

⁵⁸ Sections 111 to 116 of ISA 2007.

⁵⁹ ISA 2007

officers are over burden with traditional criminal cases and not well vast with the working and operations of the capital market to conduct criminal investigations. The delays in the prosecution of insider dealing and market abuse cases in the Nigerian capital market are sometimes caused by cumbersome and untidy process of referral of cases by SEC to criminal prosecuting authority Based on the said provisions of the ISA 2007, SEC's regulatory power on matters with criminal elements is restricted and curtailed, due to the fact that immediately it transfers such matters to law enforcement agencies, it does not have control over the matters. The law enforcement agencies are not obliged to give SEC update on the matters, even when SEC makes such request. Unfortunately, with this said situation many serious cases are handled poorly or even left without being investigated and prosecuted for no cogent reason and nothing happens, while SEC watches helplessly⁶⁰.

Again, it is found that ISA 2007⁶¹ criminalized the insider dealing offence without alternatively giving the regulator, SEC, the discretion to use civil sanction to augment the criminal punishment. This implies that SEC or other self-regulatory organizations cannot administratively punish any person/body corporate found to be involved in insider dealing offence under sections 111 and 112 as SEC can only void the transaction where necessary and order for payment of compensation to an aggrieved person as a civil remedy, unlike what is obtainable in other jurisdictions like the United Kingdom, South Africa and United States. Also, by this provision the onus of proof in criminal trial of insider dealing offence can only be punished via criminal sanction, and for prosecution to succeed it requires guilt to be proven beyond reasonable doubt. This means in practice; a successful prosecution is unlikely if there is any doubt about the alleged offence, and perhaps this could be the reason for no successful prosecution of insider dealing cases under ISA 2007.

Lastly, it is found that one of the challenges of insider dealing in the Nigeria capital market is the dearth in engagement of professionals and capacity building in the areas of detection, monitoring and investigation of insider dealing and market abuse generally. In addition, the experience of interruption in the monitoring of trades due to system break down

⁶⁰ *SEC v. Afroil Plc & 13 Ors. n. 51, p. 17.*

⁶¹ Section 115

occasioned by lack of maintenance of equipment/facilities for monitoring of trades and inability to engage professionals to manage the facilities and perform the surveillance function optimally is an impediment to fight against insider dealing.

Consequent of the above findings, the following recommendations are put forward: -

Firstly, there is need for amendment of the ISA 2007, sections 111 and 113, to include elaborate and detailed provisions that would widen the scope of the offences and defences of insider dealing in the Nigerian capital market. For instance, the provisions should be amended to include disclosures offences, where an insider discloses information to another otherwise than in the ordinary course or proper performance of his functions of his employment, office or profession; no expectation of profit defence, closed circle defence and no expectation of dealing defence as obtainable in other jurisdictions like South Africa and United Kingdom. The expansion of the offence would afford the regulators and prosecution the leverage to bring many potential offenders of insider dealing to justice, while the elaborate defences would avail and afford the potential offenders the opportunity to statutorily put-up defence for their actions, where they have cogent reasons.

Secondly, there is need to amend section 115 and make additional provisions in the ISA 2007 to empower SEC to have discretion and authority to impose civil penalties and sanctions on insider dealing violations apart from voiding the transactions and order for payment of compensation, like what is obtainable in the United States⁶² and other jurisdictions such as United Kingdom and South Africa. The provision for civil sanction and liability would be additional deterrent to potential offenders and augment the criminal penalties; and will avoid the long-drawn process of prosecution and enable SEC administer administrative punishments or file civil proceedings in court and prove its case on balance of probabilities if it deems necessary.

Thirdly, section 304 of the ISA 2007 should be expunged and replaced to give SEC power of prosecution of offences under the ISA 2007. This will eliminate delays in prosecution of insider dealing and other market abuse offences in the Nigerian capital market; remove the

⁶² Insider Trading and Securities Fraud Enforcement Act of 1988 amended US Securities Act 1934 on civil sanctions for insider trading. The Act allows the US SEC to impose stiff monetary penalties, usually in multiples of the profits generated from inside trades.

hurdles and untidy processes of referral and handing over of cases to criminal prosecuting authorities. In the interim, until section 304 of ISA 2007 is replaced, SEC needs to enter into a memorandum of understanding with Economic and Financial Crime Commission (EFCC), the Nigerian Police and office of Attorney-General of the Federation respectively on handling of cases referred by SEC to them. The memorandum of understanding would also include SEC to offer training and capacity building to the officers of the criminal prosecuting authorities on operations of capital market, in line with its market developmental role, in order to utilize the knowledge in investigation and prosecution of insider dealing offence and other market abuse cases.

In addition, SEC needs to arrange with EFCC to deploy some of its staff to EFCC on secondment, to assist in investigations of insider dealing and other market abuse related offences; while on the other hand engage officers of the Nigerian Police Force and Office of the Attorney General of the Federation on secondment for prompt investigation and prosecution of market abuse cases.

Lastly, SEC and other self-regulatory organizations like, the NGX Limited, FMDQ and NASD should have long term service agreement for maintenance of their surveillance equipment/ facilities and maintain a high-level standard in engagement and employment of staff in areas of detection, monitoring and investigation of trades generally. Emphasis should be placed on continuous capacity building of their staff in areas of surveillance, monitoring and investigations techniques, especially on market fraud, forensic and cybercrimes.